

ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА ОМОНИМИЯ ТИЛИНИНГ ФОНЕТИК-ФОНОЛОГИК, ЛЕКСИК-СЕМАНТИК ВА СИНТАКТИК САТҲ БИРЛИГИ СИФАТИДА

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Abstract: Ушбу мақолада, ўзбек тилида омонимия ходисасининг узоқ йиллардан буён тилшунослар томонидан ўрганилиб келиши, бироқ уни ўрганишда лексик-семантик саҳт бирлиги нуқтаи назаридан ёндашилгани хусусида гап боради. Шунингдек, сўнги йилларда тилшуносликда янги парадигма – антропоцентрик тилшуносликнинг юзага келиши омонимия ходисасини ҳам яна қайта кўриб чиқиш заруратини тўғдиргани, ўзбек тилшунослигида синтактик омонимия ўз ечимини кутаётган долзарб масала эканлиги қайд этилади ҳамда омонимия тилининг барча саҳт бирлиги, яъни кўпқиррали лингвистик ходиса сифатида мисоллар орқали таҳлилга тортилади.

Keywords: графологик, фонетик-фонологик, лексик-семантик, морфологик, синтактик омонимия, омонимия кўп қиррали лингвистик ходиса, прагматик омонимия, сўз ўйини, дикурсив омонимия.

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ОМОНИМИЯ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ КАК ФОНЕТИКО-ФОНОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ, ЛЕКСИКО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКАЯ И СИНТАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ЕДИНИЦА ЯЗЫКА

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Abstract: В данной статье обсуждается тот факт, что феномен омонимии на протяжении многих лет в узбекском языкознании изучался с точки зрения лексико-семантического аспекта. Также отмечается, что в последние годы появление новой парадигмы - антропоцентрической лингвистики, привело к необходимости пересмотреть феномен омонимии, как многогранное явление. В связи с этим в узбекском языкознании синтаксическая омонимия является актуальной проблемой, требующей дальнейшего исследования. В нём омонимия анализируется на примерах, как многогранное языковое явление.

Keywords: графологическая, фонетико-фонологическая, лексико-семантическая, морфологическая, синтаксическая омонимия, омонимия как многогранный языковой феномен, прагматическая омонимия, языковая игра слов, дискурсивная омонимия..

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ONOMYMY IN UZBEK LANGUAGE AS A PHONETIC-PHONOLOGICAL, LEXICO-SEMANTIC AND SYNTACTIC LEVEL

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Abstract: This article discusses the fact that the phenomenon of homonymy for many years in Uzbek linguistics has been studied from the point of view of the lexical and semantic aspect. It is also noted that in recent years the emergence of a new paradigm - anthropocentric linguistics, has led to the need to revise the phenomenon of homonymy as a multifaceted phenomenon. In this regard, in Uzbek linguistics, syntactic homonymy is an urgent problem that requires further research. In it, homonymy is analyzed by examples, as a multifaceted linguistic phenomenon.

Keywords: graphological, phonetic-phonological, lexical-semantic, morphological, syntactic homonymy, homonymy as a multifaceted linguistic phenomenon, pragmatic homonymy, linguistic wordplay, discursive homonymy...

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Introduction.

It is known that homonymy is a phenomenon specific to the Uzbek language and has been studied for many years. In particular, Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu lug'otit turk" and Alisher Navoi's "Muhokamatul lug'atayn" devoted to the interpretation of this phenomenon can be a vivid example of our opinion. Homonymy as a phenomenon of lexical level in Uzbek linguistics was deeply substantiated by Professor Sh.Rahmatullaev, its types were differentiated, as a result, the "Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek homonyms" was prepared, which fully covers the phenomenon of homonymy. Its interpretation and analysis was further improved by our leading linguist M. Mirtojiyev. As a result of the further gradual development of linguistics, the study of homonymy at the morphological level was put on the agenda, as a result, in 1975 in Uzbek linguistics M.A. Jurabaeva's dissertation "Affixal homonymy in the Uzbek language" appeared. However, it should be noted that the study of the phenomenon of homonymy in Uzbek linguistics has focused on the study of its lexical-semantic and stylistic possibilities, mainly due to its status as a lexical unit. However, in recent years, a radical shift in linguistics, that is, the emergence of the human factor in the study of linguistic phenomena and the consideration of any linguistic phenomenon in conjunction with the language carrier, has created a need to reconsider language units anthropocentric paradigm. This now allows them to come to new conclusions in their study. The phenomenon of homonymy in language and the application of such an approach in the study of homonyms has shown that homonymy is not only a lexical unit, phenomenon, but also a multifaceted phenomenon that can be studied at all stadiyes of language, especially at the syntactic This made it possible to study homonymy not only in the formal-structural aspect but also in the cognitive aspect.

The main part.

Homonymy is one of the important phenomena in creating word play in the text, as well as in creating a comic-emphonic effect in the text. It is this opportunity that makes it an integral attribute of intercultural communication. Nevertheless, homonymy is seen in the work of many researchers as a means of complicating communication. In particular, LV Malakhovsky defines homonymy as a factor that leads to the deterioration of the coding properties of language. [1: 24]. Yuqoridagi mulohazalarga asoslanib aytish mumkinki, haqiqatan ham omonimiya, ayniqsa sintaktik omonimiya, muloqotni murakkablashtiradi va matnni yoki ma'ruzachining maqsadini to'g'ri tushunishni biroz kechiktiradi, lekin shuni ham yodda tutish kerakki, u matnni estetik jihatdan ham boyitadi. For example, consider the following text:

Қўконда Урфий деган, Хўжандда Камол Хўжандий деган шоирлар бир-бирлари билан дўст экан. Камол Хўжандий Урфийни меҳмонга чақирибди. Супада суҳбат қилиб ўтирганларида Камол Хўжандийнинг кичкина кучуги дастурхон ёнига келиб, ҳатто дастурхонга тегиб кетса ҳам, у индамас экан. Урфийнинг жуда гаши келиб, аччиғи чиқибди ва охири сўрабди:- Бу махсумчага нима ном қўйганлар? Камол Хўжандий: Урфий номлардан бирини қўйганмиз-да. Урфий: Камолига етсин!

In this text *Урфий номлардан бирини қўйганмиз-да; Камолига етсин!* sentences are used in the context of the text *урфий* and *камол* it can be seen that the words created a comic effect through the homonymous possibility. However, the fact that the comic effect is intended in the text on the basis of the homonymy formed by these words makes it difficult for the recipient to understand this purpose at once.

Such texts, the most convenient and easy ways to understand language, are built on the phenomenon of homonymy. Linguist E. Kuraganov said that “the real, purposeful and creative use of homonymy is clearly seen in the humorous texts. Humor in the texts gives a new life to the homonymy by the speaker” he said. [2:173].

Indeed, in language, or rather, in speech, there is an opportunity to express concepts that are in fact completely incompatible. Such an opportunity moves at the expense of homonymy in fiction.

Alisher Navoi does the same in his work “*Яна, барча шоирлар қошида равшан ва ҳамма сўз усталари олдида аниқ маълумдирки, шеърда «тажнис ва ийҳам» (мисралар охирида жинсдош, шаклдош сўзлар ишлатиб, турли маънилар чиқариб, сўз ўйини қилиш) қоидаси умумлашгандир. Бу чиройлик ибора ва гўзал белгиларда форсидан кўра (туркчада) кўпроқ тажнисни билдиручи сўз ва ийҳамни англатучи нуқталар борки, бу назм (тизма сўз)ни безантиради ва санъатли қилади. Масалан: «от» сўзини олайлик, исм (бировнинг исми), минадиган от, тошни ёки ўқни от, деб айтилгандаги буйруқ маъноларида келади*”, he emphasizes. [2:173, 12] For example:

*Чун парию ҳурдур **отинг**, бегим,
Суръат ичра дев эрур **отинг**, бегим,*

*Ҳар хадангиким, улус андин қочар,
Нотавон жоним сари отинг, бегим.*

In this byte, too, the word *begim* in the first line means noun, in the second line “*om*” – in the meaning of the word horse, in third place, “*om*” – that it comes in the sense of action-situation proves our point above.

Such texts, on the other hand, teach the contextual understanding of the contextual meaning of unrelated words in syntactically similar syntactic constructions, the situational acceptance of a word. In addition, homonymy also helps to aestheticize communication by adding additional meaning to the text content.

According to linguist P. Giro, giving such a sentence based on homonyms in texts is a very complicated phenomenon because it has no basis for a direct semantic connection between homonyms. [3:12, 11,10]

For this reason, the study of homonymy shows that the main focus of researchers dealing with this problem is to study the use of words, the correct choice of words, the complex phenomenon of word formation.

According to traditional and foreign researchers, the realization of word play in speech at the expense of homonymy applies to several types of word play. In English, R. Alexander distinguishes between such types of word games as **graphological, phonetic-phonological, morphological, syntactic, lexical-semantic** and **pragmatic**, or **discursive** forms of word play.

-factors such as graphological / grammatical errors or technical errors / incorrectly placed spaces lead to homonymy. For example:

*Темурхон наслидин султон Улуғбек,
Ки олам кўрмади султон анингдек;*

In this text **Ки** actually considers the suffix obligatory and expresses the content of the first component of the sentence, but the diversity of rhyme, *ruk*n, weight, and text in the poem leads to homonymy.

Тенага кўтарилган қуёш ўтли тили билан ер бағридаги барча намни сўриб оларди (Ш.Рашидов) / Ранг кўр, ҳол сўр (Мақол).

*Бир парча ўт бўлиб, бунда кун,
Пахтани ишлайди ҳар кун.*

*Яхшилар инсоннинг кўнглин безар,
Ёмонлар феълидан дамлар безар.
Инсонга ой олиб бергандан кўра,
Киши кўнглини тўлдир - бекумуш безар.*

-omonymy at the phonetic-phonological stage, homophones: *Ҳамма тўртга келди / Ҳамма тортга келди. Сирини олдирди / Сирини сақлади.*

-homonymy at the morphological stage. In this form of homonymy, it is

generally assumed that the phonemes in a word structure are equivalent to morphemes. For example: *Бугун келасан- а?* / *Бугун келасан- а ?* (*таъкид, кесатиқ*); *У беи болали* / *У беиболалик каби. Авра-астарли тўн* / *Авра-астарлик тўн*; *Менинг ўғилларим* / *Менинг ўғлим*; *Бу қиз директоримизнинг қизлари* / *Бу қиз директорларимизнинг қизи* such as.

- the formation of two different meanings on the basis of the syntactic stage / verb groups / auxiliary verbs also leads to homonymy: *Ҳар ишда ҳозир (равши)* / *Ҳар ишда ҳозир (сифат) маъносида*; *Уйда бўлмоқ (жой-ўрин маъносида)* / *Уйда бўлмоқ (уйда ниманидир, тақсимламоқ-бўлмоқ маъносида)* etc.

-in graphics, spelling and punctuation: *ўртоқЛАР* - *ўрТОҚлар* - *ЎРТОҚлар*- *ўтоқЛАР*; *Кийдир (тўнни)* / *Кийдир (гапни олиб қоч)*; *ЎртоқЛАР!* *Эшик очилиб семиз, папкали одам кириб келди* / *Эшик очилиб семиз папкали, одам кириб келди*; *Сиз аҳмоқ, одам эмассиз* / *Сиз, аҳмоқ одам эмассиз* etc.

-syntactic level homonymy: *Тошкентда гўшит билан муаммо йўқми?* / *Гўшит билан Тошкентда яхши, лекин гўшитсиз Тошкентда жуда қийин*; *Ғишт қолипдан кўчди (вазият оғирлашди)* / *Ғишт қолипидан кўчди (девор қулай бошлади)*.

Conclusion.

Apparently, all of the above situations and the word play observed at all levels of language occur on the basis of homonymy. This shows that homonymy is not only a lexical-semantic level, but also a multifaceted linguistic phenomenon observed within different level units of language. The phenomenon of homonymy at the grammatical level of the language, more precisely at the syntactic level, is one of the most pressing issues in Uzbek linguistics.

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